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Implant survival after surgical treatment of early apical peri-implantitis: an ambispective cohort study covering a 20-year period

KEY WORDS

early peri-implantitis, follow-up, implant failure, implant periapical lesion, retrograde peri-implantitis, treatment survival

ABSTRACT

Purpose: To describe implant survival at least 1 year after the surgical treatment of early apical peri-implantitis (EAP) and explore potential risk factors of failure of such treatment.

Materials and methods: An ambispective cohort study was conducted, involving all patients in whom EAP was detected and surgically treated between 1996 and 2016. Reporting followed the STROBE guidelines. The time from implant placement (IP) to EAP surgery (EAPS), the diagnostic stage and intraoperative variables (location, apical lesion in the tooth being replaced, mesial and distal tooth-implant distance measured at the apex, periapical surgery of the adjacent tooth, guided bone regeneration, implant resection, explantation) were recorded to determine their impact upon treatment outcome.

Results: The initial sample consisted of 58 implants in 46 patients. The mean time from IP to EAPS was 21.7 ± 10.1 days. At the time of surgery, eight implants presented mobility and were explanted. The final sample consisted of 50 implants in 39 patients evaluated for implant survival after surgical treatment. A cumulative survival rate of 78.3% was recorded. The mean survival time of the EAP treated implants was 85.4 months (standard deviation [SD] 5.94). The diagnostic stage ($P < 0.001$) and the existence of a previous periapical lesion in the tooth being replaced ($P = 0.022$) had a significant influence upon implant survival.

Conclusions: The cumulative survival rate was 78.3%, with a mean survival time of 85.4 months. The diagnostic stage of EAP and the presence of a lesion in the tooth being replaced significantly influenced the survival of implants with EAP subjected to surgical treatment.

Conflict of interest statement: *The authors declare no conflicts of interest related to this study.*

*First and second authors claim equal authorship.

Introduction

Early apical peri-implantitis (EAP) or implant periapical disease develops in the tissues around the apex of a dental implant¹ after placement, causing osseointegration failure, while the bone

architecture is initially maintained in the coronal portion². The reported incidence of EAP is low ($0.26 - 7.8\%$)²⁻⁵. The diagnosis of EAP is based on symptoms (pain and tightness), clinical signs (swelling, fistula and drainage) and radiographic findings (radiolucency around the implant apex)⁶.

Fig 1 Study flow chart.

The implementation of new imaging technologies such as small-volume cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) is helpful in establishing an early diagnosis, showing a clear clinical image of periapical implant bone loss⁶. The early diagnosis and management of active EAP includes surgery and follow-up to assess treatment success and avoid implant failure⁷.

As a differential diagnosis, a periapical radiolucency can be attributable to deeper drilling than the implant requires, with no associated clinical symptoms. This condition is considered to be inactive, and no treatment is required provided stability is maintained over the follow-up⁸. There are also failed osseointegration processes that course with signs and symptoms similar to those of EAP, and which are a consequence of three-dimensionally incorrect implant placement (flapless implant placement, fenestration of the buccal plate)

or infections of the biomaterials employed⁶. The literature describes medical^{4,9} as well as surgical approaches to the management of EAP^{2,4,10-15}, and in this regard most studies involving surgical treatment describe restitutio ad integrum.

The aim of surgery is to eliminate the infectious-inflammatory process and allow osseointegration to be restored. Surgical treatment includes anaesthesia, incision, the raising of a full thickness flap, ostectomy, apical curettage and abundant irrigation with saline solution^{1,10,16} or chlorhexidine^{4,17}.

Some studies describe the use of biomaterials, with or without membranes, to achieve complete bone regeneration of the defect^{2,10,11,13-15,17}. Sectioning of the apex of the implant is recommended in those cases where access to the granulation tissue cannot be otherwise ensured, as well as when there is an anatomical relationship with the maxillary sinus or nasal cavity¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Regarding the prognosis after surgical treatment of EAP, the information in the literature is limited. Only four studies^{5,10,19,20} provide data on implant survival and specify the follow-up period. The reported survival rates range from 73.2 to 97.4%, with a follow-up of 1 to 10 years^{5,10,19,20}. None of the available studies have addressed which factors may influence the prognosis after surgical treatment of EAP.

The primary aim of this study was to evaluate implant survival after the surgical treatment of EAP. The secondary aim was to identify potential risk factors that could influence the prognosis of implants with EAP after surgical treatment.

Materials and methods

Study design

An ambispective single cohort study was carried out following the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) statement²¹ (Fig 1), at the Department of Oral Surgery, Faculty of Medicine and Dentistry, University of Valencia, Spain, between 1996 and 2016, including all patients subjected to surgical treatment of EAP.

In the period between 1996 and 2010, a retrospective cohort analysis was made of 22 implants, which has been described in two previous publications^{5,10}. The follow-up was subsequently continued. From 2010 onwards, the new patients diagnosed with EAP and subjected to surgical treatment were studied on a prospective basis. All patients treated at the university were informed and signed a consent to the use of their data for teaching and research purposes. The study design was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Valencia (Ref. H1478255958653).

Sample selection

The following inclusion criteria were used: 1) symptoms and signs of EAP after implant placement; 2) presence or absence of a radiolucency around the implant apex; 3) dull percussion of non-submerged implants; 4) absence of implant mobility during the diagnostic phase; 5) patients \geq 18 years of age subjected to treatment with implants; and 6) no serious disease or condition known to alter bone metabolism. The exclusion criteria were: 1) inadequate implant positioning or implant placement with guided bone regeneration (as this could confound correct diagnosis and introduce possible sample bias); and 2) implant mobility detected while performing the surgical treatment.

Surgical technique

All surgeries were performed by an experienced surgeon (MPD). Infiltrative locoregional anaesthesia was provided with 4% articaine and 1:100,000 adrenaline (Inibsa, Lliçà de Vall, Barcelona, Spain). After submarginal incision, a full-thickness flap was raised and an osteotomy was carried out using a round 0.27 mm tungsten carbide bur (Jota, Switzerland) mounted in a handpiece with abundant irrigation. Surgical curettage of the cavity and implant surface was performed with ultrasound (Piezon Master 700, EMS Electro Medical Systems, Switzerland) and curettes (Double Gracey Mini Anterior/Posterior, American Eagle Instruments, Missoula, USA), under profuse irrigation with sterile saline solution to eliminate possible remains.

When the adjacent tooth showed an apical lesion, root canal therapy or periapical surgery (if the tooth had been endodontically treated) was performed. Before closure and when the marginal defects were wide, a collagen membrane was placed to avoid soft tissue infiltration at the apex of the implant and to improve new bone formation in the cavity⁶. Tensionless soft tissue closure was performed with 6/0 polyamide sutures (Seralon, Serag-Wiessner, Germany).

One hour before surgery, we administered 2 g of amoxicillin (600 mg clindamycin in patients allergic to amoxicillin) and 0.12% chlorhexidine, plus 0.05% cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC) rinse (Perio Aid, Dentaïd, Barcelona, Spain) for 1 minute before anaesthetising the patient. Postoperatively, all patients were prescribed with 500 mg of amoxicillin and 250 mg metronidazole (600 mg clindamycin in patients allergic to amoxicillin) every 8 hours for 7 days; 25 mg dexketoprofen upon demand; and 0.12% chlorhexidine plus 0.05% CPC rinse twice daily for 10 days. Sutures were removed after 1 week. Clinical and radiological follow-up was performed after 1, 3, 6, 9 and 12 months, with annual controls thereafter.

Data collection

A series of parameters at the time of implant placement were recorded: patient gender, age, presence of periapical disease in the tooth being replaced by the implant, and mesial and distal tooth-implant distance measured at the apex (classified as \leq 1.5 mm or $>$ 1.5 mm) (Fig 2a). During EAP surgery (EAPS) we recorded the following: time from implant placement (IP) to EAPS, EAP location and classification⁷, periapical surgery of the adjacent tooth, implant resection and explantation (the implant being explanted if mobility was noticed after removal of the granulation tissue).

The final outcome was assessed as either failure or survival of the implant.

Intra-oral radiographs (VistaScan, Dürr Dental, Bietigheim-Bissingen, Germany) and CBCT scans (Planmeca Promax Mid) were used to diagnose implant periapical lesions. The CBCT images were visualised using Planmeca Romexis software on a

Fig 2a-d

(a) Schematic representation of the mesial and distal apical measurement; (b-d) Mesial and distal apical measurement in intra-oral radiographs.

21.5-inch monitor (iMac, Apple, Cupertino, CA, USA). Radiographs were taken using a parallelisation method with a Rinn XCP ring positioner (Dentsply, Constanz, Germany). The measurements of distances were calibrated using the known implant platform diameter with DBSWIN imaging software (Dürr Dental). The measures of the apical distances between teeth and implants were determined using four stable references on the radiographs. Two reference points were established at the implant neck: one mesial (A) and one distal (B) (Fig 2a). The other two reference points (C and D) were established at the apical part of the implant: mesial and distal, respectively. The distance between the axial axis of the tooth and the apical references was recorded (Fig 2a and 2b-d).

The classification proposed by Peñarrocha et al⁷ was used to establish the diagnostic stage of EAP: non-suppurative; suppurative; or subacute. The surgical treatment was performed in

non-suppurated acute stages in the presence of symptoms (pain), and in acute suppurative and subacute stages in the presence of symptoms and the absence of implant mobility. If the implant had a radiolucent area (not presenting after surgery as a result of over-drilling but manifesting over time), with no pain, the lesion was monitored without medical treatment (Fig 3).

Statistical analysis

A biostatistician with expertise in dentistry analysed all the data. The statistical analysis was carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 21 for Macintosh, SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). Statistical significance was considered for $P < 0.05$. The time from implant placement to EAPS, location, diagnostic stage and clinical signs and symptoms, implants with non-detectable mobility during the diagnostic phase

Fig 3 Decision making flow chart.

were analysed (initial study sample). For these variables the mean, standard deviation (SD), minimum, maximum and median (for continuous parameters) and absolute and relative frequencies (for categorical parameters) were calculated. To describe survival, we analysed the implants in which EAPS was successfully performed. Survival analysis was based on the Kaplan-Meier method, estimating the survival function for the time in which each event occurs. Mean survival, standard error and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated, based on data approximation to a normal distribution. The log-rank test was used to determine whether the different patient or lesion parameters generated significantly different survival curves. The variables detected as being significant or nearly significant ($P < 0.1$) were entered in the

Cox regression model. An average of more than one implant was evaluated per patient, therefore, the same statistical models described above were estimated including only one randomly selected implant per patient to avoid bias.

Results

The initial study sample consisted of 58 implants in 46 patients – 32 female (69.6%) and 14 male (30.4%) – with a mean age of 51.9 years (SD 11.9).

The mean time from IP to EAPS was 21.7 ± 10.1 days (range 6 to 50 days). Figure 4 shows the average time from IP to EAPS, distributed according to periods. Table 1 details the distribution according to tooth and arch. In terms of

Table 1 Distribution of early peri-implantitis according to tooth and arch

Type of tooth	Total		Maxillary		Mandibular	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
	58	100.0%	23	39.7%	35	60.3%
Incisors	20	34.5%	7	12.1%	13	22.4%
Canines	10	17.2%	5	8.6%	5	8.6%
Premolars	23	39.7%	9	15.5%	14	24.2%
Molars	5	8.6%	2	3.4%	3	5.2%

Table 2 Signs and symptoms according to the diagnostic stage

Signs and symptoms		Total		Non-suppurative		Suppurative		Subacute	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Pus	Total	58	100%	28	100%	23	100%	7	100%
	No	28	48.3%	28	100%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
	Yes	30	51.7%	0	0.0%	23	100%	7	100%
Pain	Total	58	100%	28	100%	23	100%	7	100%
	No	8	13.8%	8	28.6%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
	Yes	50	86.2%	20	71.4%	23	100%	7	100%
Inflammation	Total	58	100%	28	100%	23	100%	7	100%
	Yes	58	100%	28	100%	23	100%	7	100%
Radiographic alterations	Total	58	100%	28	100%	23	100%	7	100%
	No	17	29.3%	14	50.0%	3	13.0%	0	0.0%
	Yes	41	70.7%	14	50.0%	20	87.0%	7	100%

diagnostic stage⁷, 28 implants were in the acute non-suppurative stage (48.3%), 23 in the acute suppurative stage (39.7%) and 7 in the subacute stage (12.1%). Table 2 details the signs and symptoms according the diagnostic stage.

Fig 4 Mean time from implant placement (IP) to early apical peri-implantitis surgery (EAPS).

At the time of EAPS, after raising of the muco-periosteal flap and removal of the granulation tissue, eight implants presented mobility and were explanted. These implants were therefore excluded from the survival analysis. Most explanted implants were located in the region of the maxillary incisors (27.8%) and maxillary premolars (27.8%), followed by the mandibular incisors (16.7%); the rest of the locations represented 27.5%.

Thus, the final study sample consisted of 50 implants in 39 patients – 28 female (71.8%) and 11 male (28.2%) – with a mean age of 49.7 years (SD 10.3), in which surgical treatment was successfully performed.

After EAPS, 10 implants failed during the observation period, while 40 survived at the end of the study period. The mean survival time of the EAP treated implants was 85.4 months (SD 5.94) (range 0.3 to 107 months). A cumulative survival

Table 3 Survival of treated early peri-implantitis with a maximum follow-up of 107 months

Months	Implants at start	Failed implants	Failure rate for period	Cumulative survival rate
0–3	50	4	8.0%	92.0%
3–6	46	4	8.7%	84.0%
6–12	42	1	2.4%	82.0%
12–18	37	0	0.0%	82.0%
18–24	34	0	0.0%	82.0%
24–48	30	1	3.3%	78.3%
48–107	20	0	0.0%	78.3%

rate of 78.3% was obtained for the EAP treated implants (Table 3).

Regarding diagnostic stage, an early diagnosis had a statistically significant impact upon implant survival ($P < 0.001$) (Table 4) (Fig 5). A diagnosis in the subacute stage multiplied the risk of implant failure 9.35-fold with respect to diagnosis in the acute non-suppurative stage during the first months after implant placement. The Cox regression model yielded the following summarising equation:

$$H(t) = H_0(t) 1.64^{acute\ suppurative} 9.35^{subacute} 3.34^{apical\ lesion\ in\ tooth\ being\ replaced}$$

Treated EAP in which the tooth being replaced had a periapical lesion showed lower mean survival values (58.3 months; CI 38.6 – 77.9) than implants placed in non-pathological sites (69.3 months; CI 58.0 – 80.4). A significant relationship was found between the presence of an apical lesion in the tooth being replaced and implant survival ($P = 0.022$) (Table 4).

Regarding the mesial tooth-implant distance measured at the apex, when the mesial distance was ≤ 1.5 mm, the probability of failure was greater. It was only possible to register this parameter in 20 patients; shortcomings in statistical power therefore did not allow the direct detection of significant differences ($P = 0.190$) (Table 4). Regarding the distal distance, only one implant was placed at a distance of less than 1.5 mm; consequently, it was not possible to describe the results statistically.

In 6 cases (10.3%) the periapical surgery of the adjacent tooth had to be performed intraoperatively

Fig 5 Mean implant survival (months) according to diagnostic stage.

Table 4 Log-rank test of homogeneity of survival function according to factors

Factors	P value
Age	0.255
Gender	0.229
Location of the tooth (incisor/canine/premolar/molar)	1.000
Maxilla/mandible	0.250
Lesion in tooth being replaced	0.022*
Apical mesial distance (> 1.5 mm)	0.190
Apical distal distance (> 1.5 mm)	0.700
Immediate/delayed placement	0.054
Diagnostic stage	< 0.001***
Time from implant placement to early peri-implantitis surgery	0.317

* $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$

to eliminate the source of infection and ensure tissue healing. Guided bone regeneration proved necessary in 10 cases (17.2%) to avoid tissue collapse in the presence of wide marginal defects. In four cases (6.9%) complete debridement of the lesion could not be performed, so the implant apex was sectioned to improve access to the bony crypt. Shortcomings in statistical power did not allow the direct detection of significant differences in relation to these variables.

Discussion

The present study describes 58 cases of EAP, with implant survival being assessed at least 1 year after EAPs in 50 implants.

With regard to the moment in which the condition is diagnosed, the literature describes that the radiological findings usually manifest between 7 to 16 days after surgery^{4,5,22} to 3 months after implant placement^{16,17,23,24}. Our findings (21.7 ± 10.1 days) are consistent with those described in the literature.

The relationship between diagnostic stage and survival has not been studied in the literature. In the present study a statistically significant association was found between the diagnostic stage and implant survival ($P < 0.001$) – the subacute stage being seen to multiple the risk of implant failure 9.35-fold with respect to the acute non-suppurative stage. These data suggest that early diagnosis and correct treatment of EAP are crucial.

Several authors^{2,20} have indicated that the dental history of the implant site is of great importance. Implant placement to replace a tooth with a periapical lesion or subjected to endodontic treatment is respectively associated to a 32.3- and 7.56-fold increase in the risk of developing a lesion around the implant apex²⁰. In our study the presence of a lesion in the tooth being replaced was significantly related to implant survival ($P = 0.022$).

Depending on the condition of the adjacent teeth, the recommendation is to provide root canal therapy or perform periapical surgery if the adjacent tooth that has been subjected to endodontic treatment. It should be taken into account

that in the present study a periapical surgery of the tooth was performed in those cases where contamination was originated from the tooth or as a result of excessive proximity to the adjacent tooth.

No previous studies have examined the apical tooth-implant distance in relation to implant survival. The statistical power of our sample did not allow the detection of significant differences in survival among the treated implants ($P = 0.202$).

Consensus is lacking on the therapeutic strategy best suited for the management of EAP. Since the first description of implant periapical lesions in 1992, the management approach has been surgical, based on the total thickness flap release with curettage of the bony defect to remove granulation tissue and detoxify the implant surface. Some studies have described the use of bone regeneration materials, accompanied or not by tissue regeneration barriers, to achieve complete bone regeneration of the defect^{2,11,13-15,17}. Some authors^{18,25,26} have described a resection of the implant when access to the bone crypt was not guaranteed for removal of all the granulation tissue.

To date, only three articles have described implant survival in EAP. Balshi et al¹⁹, in a series of 39 implants with periapical disease and a mean follow-up of 4.54 years, reported a treated implant survival rate of 97.4%. Lefever et al²⁰, with a maximum follow-up of 126 months, recorded a cumulative survival rate (CSR) of 73.2%. Peñarrocha et al⁵, in a series of 22 EAP lesions and a maximum follow-up of 72 months, described a CSR of 91%. Our results are consistent with those of Lefever et al²⁰, with a maximum follow-up of 107 months and a CSR of 67.5%.

Although the management of EAP remains empirical, surgical treatment to remove all granulation tissue appears to suffice to avoid the progression of bone destruction and consequent loss of the implant. Further studies involving larger samples are needed to identify possible significant associations between variables such as guided bone regeneration, periapical surgery of the adjacent tooth or sectioning of the implant apex and implant survival in cases of EAP subjected to treatment.

The relevance of our study is that it allowed us to know the survival of the EAP treated implants with respect to the different diagnostic stages and their relationship with other surgical variables. A limitation of the study is its ambispective methodological design, due to the characteristics of this lesion and the difficulty – because of the low incidence of EAP – of securing a large study sample. A clinical limitation was to conduct the surgery in a way as similar as possible, individualising the characteristics presented by each clinical case. More extensive and long-term studies are needed to describe implant survival after the treatment of EAP.

Conclusions

The cumulative implant survival rate was 78.3% with a mean survival of 85.4 months. The diagnostic stage of EAP and the presence of a lesion in the tooth being replaced, significantly influenced the survival of implants with EAP subjected to surgical treatment.

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